

Determination of Quality Criteria and Performance of Urban Parks; The Case of Söke Urban Park

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Abstract

Open and green spaces and especially urban parks play an important role in improving the quality of urban life. Urban parks provide multifaceted social, environmental, economic, cultural and aesthetic services and contributions to the urban people and urban ecosystem. The aim of this study is to determine the basic/sub-criteria of quality performance of existing urban parks and to test them on the scale of urban parks. In this study, as a result of the evaluation by 50 experts, a total of 9 basic criteria (spatial usability, vegetative design and usability, aesthetic appearance, structure/material design and suitability for use, transportation and accessibility, comfort and perception, social communication level, ecosystem services), 81 sub-criteria and weight scores were determined and the urban parks quality performance "KE PA KAP" model was created. In this proposed model, according to the basic and sub-criteria, the current quality performance of Söke Zeytindalı Urban Park was evaluated and it was determined that the quality performance of the park was at a medium level with a total score of 32.24.

Keywords: Urban park, Quality criteria, Performance evaluation, KE-PA-KAP model, Soke- Zeytindalı urban park.

Kent Parklarının Kalite Ölçütleri ve Performansının Belirlenmesi; Söke Kent Parkı Örneği

Öz

Kentsel yaşam kalitesinin artırılmasında açık ve yeşil alanlar ve özellikle kent parkları önemli rol üstlenmektedir. Kent parkları kent insanına ve kent ekosistemine çok yönlü sosyal, çevresel, ekonomik, kültürel ve estetik vb hizmet ve katkılar sağlamaktadır. Bu çalışmanın amacı; mevcut kent parklarının kalite performans temel/alt ölçütlerin belirlenmesi ve kent parkı ölçeğinde test edilmesidir. Bu çalışmada 50 uzman tarafından değerlendirme yapılması sonucunda toplam 9 temel ölçüt (mekânsal kullanılabilirlik, bitkisel tasarım ve kullanılabilirlik, estetik görünüm, yapı/malzeme tasarım ve kullanım uygunluğu, ulaşım ve erişilebilirlik, konfor ve algı durumu, sosyal iletişim düzeyi, ekosistem hizmetleri), 81 alt ölçüt ve ağırlık puanları tespit edilmiş ve "KE PA KAP" modeli oluşturulmuştur. Önerilen bu modelde temel ve alt ölçütlerine göre Söke Kenti Zeytindalı kent parkının mevcut kalite performans değerlendirmesi yapılarak toplam 32,24 puan ile parkın kalite performansının orta düzeyde olduğu belirlenmiştir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Kent parkı, Kalite ölçütleri, Performans değerlendirme, KE-PA-KA-P modeli, Söke- Zeytindalı kent parkı.

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1. Introduction

Urban areas, as a lifestyle and space shaped by people's collective life instincts and socialization tendencies, are considered as the starting point in the history of civilization (Boyacı 2010). Cities are not only a collection of buildings that meet people's need for shelter, but also places that harbor all kinds of social relations (Gül & Küçük 2001).

Today, the rapid population growth of cities and settlements with high gravitational power and the multifaceted demands of many sectors (housing, service, commercial, education, industry, etc.) and related actors, the tendency to obtain effortless economic benefits (rent), etc. factors have led to unhealthy and irregular cities and urbanization. As a result, the quality of life of the city is decreasing day by day as a result of negative factors such as mechanized, horizontal and vertical block constructions, heavy vehicle traffic, environmental pollution, visual pollution, crowding, noise, natural disasters, infrastructure and superstructure inadequacies, destruction or reduction of open and green areas, destruction or overuse of water resources, etc. As a result of urbanization trends and activities, factors such as roads, buildings, sidewalks, technological tools and equipment, heating and cooling activities, vehicle traffic, reduction of green areas cause the heat island effect in the city. This leads to more CO₂ emissions into the atmosphere. Urban people, who have to live with all these undesirable negativities, are no longer satisfied with meeting their basic needs, but turn to natural/forested areas or green areas in or near the city to get away from these negativities and to relieve their tensions that cause various mental and intellectual disorders. These areas are not only places where the instant human-nature relationship is realized, but also places where this relationship (Gezer & Gül, 2009).

Accordingly, the inadequacy of the quantity and quality of existing and available open and green areas and green tissue elements in response to the recreational and entertainment needs in cities brings to the agenda the need for aesthetic and functional services and contributions provided by trees and forests to urban ecology and quality of life (Gezer & Gül, 2009; Gül et al., 2020; Gül et al., 2024).

Open and green areas in urban areas are among the basic concepts that reveal and shape the physical structure of the city and are a balance element that integrates other land uses. Open and green areas have aesthetic and various functional features (such as reducing noise, cleaning the air, creating a microclimate effect) in balancing the deteriorating relationship between man and nature and improving urban living conditions. For this reason, the quality and quantity of open and green areas in developed countries are accepted as an indicator of civilization and quality of life (Gül et al., 2020; Gül et al., 2024).

Urban parks are both an urban element and a social and public space in terms of creating green space systems within the city and ensuring the continuity of this system (Gezer & Gül, 2009; Sarı, 2019).

Urban parks are public spaces designed to serve the entire city and meet the need for a place where individuals can socialize and relax away from the stress of busy urban life. Urban parks offer important recreational and entertainment opportunities for city dwellers with their flexible use and a variety of physical activities. Urban parks are spaces where everyone, regardless of income, culture and lifestyle, can come together, communicate, interact, share art and culture, and engage in various recreational activities. In addition to these values, they are important areas that provide balance and buffer space between different physical spaces in the urban area, increase ecological quality, improve the microclimate of the city, connect with the nature of the city, contribute to the oxygenation of the city thanks to its biological diversity, provide light and air, and reduce noise pollution. In addition, urban parks play an important role in the promotion of cities and as identity values. They bring individuals together and make urban life healthier by hosting various activities (Gül & Küçük 2001; Serin & Gül, 2006; Gezer & Gül, 2009; Erduran & Kabaş, 2010; Öztürk, 2013; Ocağ, 2014; Gül et al., 2020; Güngör & Çakın, 2021; Türker & Gül, 2022; Varol & Tutkun, 2023; Şahin & Tunçay, 2023; Soydan, 2024).

Urban parks are green areas with active and passive recreation opportunities, which are used by people of all age groups, usually spread over an area of 400 acres or more and located within 30-60 minutes walking distance. Urban parks are not only small areas but also comprehensive parks with various uses such as amphitheaters, water features, children's playgrounds, sports complexes, zoos and restaurants. Urban parks are various service areas that develop as a natural part of urban life within the complex urban order and play an important role in maintaining the balance between nature and humans (Yazici, 2019).

In order for urban parks to make multifaceted contributions and services to the city and its people, they should be designed in accordance with their purpose and their management should be effectively maintained. For this purpose, monitoring existing urban parks, evaluating their perceptions about the park and determining their quality performance are of great importance in terms of sustainability and quality (Yücel & Yıldızcı, 2010; Çakır & Gül, 2024).

The quality indicators of parks can vary according to the activities and uses, diversity of activities, accessibility, perceivability, comfort and image of the park, maintenance and security of the park, and sense of belonging (Başalma et al., 2017).

Monitoring and determining the current performance of urban parks can provide important facilities for improving and developing the quality of the park and increase user satisfaction.

The main aim of this study is to determine the quality basic/sub-criteria and indicators for the quality performance of an existing urban park, to test the quality performance model to be developed in this context to be applied on Söke Zeytindalı Urban Park and to make strategic suggestions within the scope of the deficiencies of the urban park. Thus, with An urban parks quality performance (KE-PA-KA-P) model created, it will be possible to make decisions, actions and improvement studies of the current situation to be taken in the planning / design and management / governance according to the quality performance status of the newly designed or existing urban parks.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Material

The main material of the study is Zeytindalı Urban Park located in Söke District of Aydın Province. Data on urban green areas were obtained from Söke Municipality Directorate of Parks and Gardens and Zeytindalı Urban Park was selected as the study area due to its area size and the most intensive use. The current situation in the selected area was examined through on-site observation, photographed and analyzed. After the selection of the study area, the plan and general views of the park were photographed with drone images and on-site observations were made. Then, with the KE-PA-KA-P model created, the quality performance of the selected park was analyzed and accordingly, deficiencies were identified and solutions were developed.

2.1.1. General information about the research area

Söke urban is located between 37°45' North latitude and 27°24' East longitude. It is 54 km to Aydın, 56 km to Didim, 23 km to Kuşadası and 120 km to İzmir. The surface area of Söke district center is 20.93 km². The total population of Söke City center in 2024 is 79195 (Table 1) (TÜİK, 2024). Zeytindalı Urban Park, which was selected as the research area, is located in Söke City (Figure 1-2).

WORK AREA LOCATION MAP

Figure 1. Study area location map (From author's archive)

Figure 2. Location of Zeytindalı Park (Open Street Map, 2025)

There are 8 neighborhoods in Söke city scale. The amounts of green areas connected to these neighborhoods are calculated as 30.719,28 m² in Atatürk Neighborhood; 17.030,15 m² in Cumhuriyet Neighborhood; 27.609,04 m² in Çeltikçi Neighborhood; 5121,898 m² in Fevzipaşa Neighborhood; 29.481,66 m² in Yenicami Neighborhood; 15.844,13 m² in Yenikent Neighborhood; 20.092,2 m² in Konak Neighborhood; 13.808,46 m² in Kemalpaşa Neighborhood. Based on these measurements, Söke city center has a total green area of 159,706.8 m². Green area types and area sizes of each neighborhood (Figure 3) are given in (Table 1).

Figure 3. Söke City plan (Söke Belediyesi, 2024a)

Table 1. Green areas and their sizes in Söke City Center (Söke Belediyesi, 2024a)

Atatürk Neighborhood	Green Area Name	Area Size (m ²)
Mustafa Arıcı-Köknar Street	Hasan Cakir Park	727,85
New Site Square, Kavak-Oak Street	Martyr Hakkı Uyar Park	3930,10
River Street Park	Martyr Suleyman Teke Park	1681,44
Abdi Ipekci Street Park	Martyr Remzi İlboğa Park	342
In front of the Regional Traffic Directorate	Traffic Education Park	1589,86
Çaylar Street-Kavak Street	Martyr Arif Kaplan Park	1390,83
Turgut Özal Street, next to the Old İşKur	Umut Vural Disabled Park	1398,09
Ali Eröz Street Park	Martyr Sevinç Çelik Park	637
Yayla Street	Martyr Murat Yıldızgünlü Park	1756,41
Hanimeli Street Park	Park	595
Seven Street Park	Park	538,34
Hoca Ahmet Yesevi Street	Ugur Mumcu Park	9950,62
Cankiri Street	Green Area	(284,21-157,43-289,1)
Çankırı Street-Ekrem Karakaş Street Park	Green Area	360
Türkan Saylan	Road + DD Area	5091
Total		30.719,28
Cumhuriyet Neighborhood	Green Area Name	Area Size (m ²)
Öner Street – Anadolu Street	Dear Teacher Park	2154,89
Koçlar Street Park	Martyr Mustafa Korkmaz Park	3522,9
Kıvanç Street Park	Martyr Ercan Ozgun Park	1177+360

Tekeli Street-Duru Street	Children's Playground	385,36
Ataturk Street	Martyr Ferdi Bolat Park	1479+824+220
School Street Park	Martyr Kamil Çırpan Park	1054
Okul Street-Yeltepe Street	Martyr Kadir Rençber Park	1321
Cumhuriyet Neighborhood	Turker Street Park	422
Subaşı Street Park	Green Area	489
Cumhuriyet Neighborhood. Nadide St.	Martyr Serkan Altınkaynak Park	812
Garbage Skewers	Green Fields	947
In front of the Alp Tunga Site	Green Areas	1071
Industrial Apprenticeship Training Side	Green Area	791
Total		17.030,15
Çeltikçi Neighborhood	Green Area Name	Area Size (m²)
Batman-Beyazit Street Park	Martyr Tufan Aydın Park	2174,526
Behind Teacher's House	Süner Street Park	384,26
Next to the Park in Örnek Building Coop.	Martyr Şerif Caliskan Park	2319,92
Oylum Street Park	Park	361,54
Mini Street Park	Park	634
Yıldız-Günay Street Inside Söke Sports Facilities	Children's Playground	136
National Sovereignty Street Park	Güngör Pura Parkı	3703
Poet Orhan Veli Street.	Barış Manço Parkı	6358,89
National Sovereignty Street	Adalet Parkı	7304,51
Zekai Avcıoğlu Street	Children's Playground	460
100th Anniversary Memorial Park	Children's Playground	2074
Sevindik Street	Green Area	167,39
Neighborhood House and Surrounding Green Areas	Green Area	1043+488
Total		27.609,04
Fevzipaşa Neighborhood	Green Area Name	Area Size (m²)
Aysel Kertmen – R.I.Ozsoy Street Park	Martyr Mustafa Ozdemir Park	1594,10
Staple Street Park	Park	344,798
Parking area next to Fevzipaşa Police Station	Martyr Policeman Zeki Esmer Park	350
Gez Street Park	Cemali Gez Park	438
Red Church Streamside Park	Martyr Murat Ali Yardım Park	1075
Faik Kocagöz Street	Park in front of the Mukhtar's Office	841
Kayas Street Parking Lot	Green Area Arrangement	479
Total		5121,898
Yenicami Neighborhood	Green Area Name	Area Size (m²)
Turhal Street	Intersection of Tümen Street and Ural Street	768,428
Bilecik Street	Children's Playground	318,11
Kemal Yavuz Street	Martyr Hüseyin Bayonet Park	2117,86

I. Sirin Street Park	Martyr Mehmet Edremitli Park	1764,40
Mahmut Savran Street	Martyr Omer Ozogul Park	1578,81
Konyalılar Neighborhood	Osman Dinç Street Park	335
Konyalılar Neighborhood	Muzaffer İlkesen Street Park	220
Ali Yaman Street-Beyza Street	Martyr Mehmet Ali Birlik Park	371,23
Hilmi Ziya Postacı Street Park	Martyr Celal Isen Park	1467,71
Zahire Marketing	Farm Street Park	675,52
M.Evkuran Street, Nihat Aşkın Street.	Martyr Tahsin Yildirim Park	2523
Behzat Ulusoy Street-S.Uzgun Street	Martyr Mehmet Kaya Çergin Park	1775
Bağarası Street Park	Grandmother Torun Park	1973
Senirmak Street	Next to Stage Construction Coop. Park	743
Pelin Street	6 September Park	6063
Eren Yildirim Street	Suleyman Seba Park	2790
Next to the fire station	Green Area	1280,719
Mukhtar's Office Building Garden	Green Area	380
Tan Street	Green Area	771,87
Fig Street	Median Strips and Green Areas	1059
Kasımpatı Street	Medians	97
Mine Street	Green Area	246
Next to the cocoon houses	Green Area	163
Total		29.481,66
Yenikent Neighborhood	Green Area Name	Area Size (m²)
89th Street Sports Fields	Tarık Akan Park	2784
Park next to Megakent Building	Park	559
33rd Street - 31st Street	Park	1535
10th Street - 17th Street	Park	848
15th Street-Mehmet Semerci Street intersection	Zeytindalı City Park + Parking Lot	4132 + 705,13
38th Street	Green Area	825
43rd Street	Green Area	1110
44th Street	Park and Green Area	1352
44th Street	Park and Green Area	1994
Total		15.844,13
Konak Neighborhood	Green Area Name	Area Size (m²)
Park next to Abalaki Mosque	Park	666
Onur Street	Children's Playground	1532,13
Namık Kemal Street. İnci Street	Recep Yazıcıoğlu Park	1191,65
Konak Neighborhood. Aydın Street	Ataturk Park	14337,42
Friends Street	Green Area	810
Government Square	Green Area	1133
Opposite Ataturk Primary School	Green Area and Parking	422

Total		20.092,2
Kemalpaşa Neighborhood	Green Area Name	Area Size (m²)
Koza Street	Halime's Creek Park	2400
Kemalpaşa Neighborhood	Martyrs and Veterans Park	10941
Football Street	Median strip and Green Areas	368,49 +98.97
Alay Street	Green Area	666.7
Total		13.808,46
GRAND TOTAL		159.706,8

The population distribution of Söke City Central Neighborhoods is as follows. Atatürk Neighborhood: 11652, Cumhuriyet Neighborhood: 7229, Çeltikçi Neighborhood: 13416, Fevzipasa Neighborhood: 7124, Yenicami Neighborhood: 15358, Yenikent Mahallesi: 11172, Konak Mahallesi: 11552, Kemalpaşa Neighborhood: 4146, totaling 81,649 (Nüfusune, 2024). The average amount of green space per capita in Söke is 1.96 m² and is very insufficient (Table 2).

Table 2. The amount of green space per capita according to the neighborhood population of Söke City (Söke Municipality, 2024b)

Neighborhood Name	Number of Active Open-Green Areas	Current Active Open-Green Area (m²)	Current Active Open-Green Area per Capita (m²)
Atatürk	15	30719,28	2,63
Cumhuriyet	13	17030,15	2,35
Celtikçi	13	27609,04	2,05
Fevzipaşa	7	5121,9	0,71
Yenicami	24	29481,66	1,91
Yenikent	9	15844,13	1,41
Konak	7	20092,2	1,73
Kemalpaşa	4	14475,16	3,49
TOTAL	92	160373,5	16,28
Average			1,96

2.1.2. General information about Zeytindalı Urban Park

Zeytindalı Urban Park is 4,837 m² in size within the borders of Yenikent Neighborhood (Figure 4). It includes a children's playground, fitness area, walking paths, bicycle paths, ornamental pools, bridges, seating areas, businesses and green areas. Söke Business Faculty is located in a location where student dormitories, cafes and restaurants are densely populated. In terms of transportation, the park is located at a central point where it is easy to reach the city stops and many districts of Söke by minibuss and bus.

Figure 4. General view of Atatürk Park (From authors' archive)

2.2. Method

Within the scope of the research, the suitability of Zeytindalı Urban Park in Söke in terms of quality criteria and related standards is discussed from the perspective of landscape architecture. In this direction; the study was carried out in 4 stages; “Literature Review and Creation of Background Plots”, “Determination of Basic / Sub Criteria of Urban Park Quality Performance”, “Zeytindalı Urban Park Survey Study”, “Evaluation and Synthesis”.

Domestic and foreign literature on the subject was reviewed. In this context, urban parks, park quality criteria, performance evaluation, etc. were examined and a conceptual framework was created. In addition, numerical bases for the green areas of Söke City were created and general information was obtained.

For this purpose, the main/sub-criteria for the quality performance of urban parks were first analyzed by reviewing the literature (Table 3). The basic / sub-criteria used in the literature for the quality of urban parks were classified according to the conditions of our country and determined as a result of expert evaluations and weight scores were determined.

Table 3. Basic/sub-criteria used in the literature for the quality of urban parks

Sources	Criteria Used
Gülersoy et al., (2009)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Livability; Character, Connection, Mobility, Individual freedom, Diversity, • Survival; Individuality, Health, Environment, Comfort, Safety and Security • Character; Sense of Place/Spirit, Sincerity, Sense of Time, Stability, Aesthetics • Connection; Compatibility, Continuity, Integrity, Symbolism, Interaction, Belonging • Mobility; Accessibility, Convenience, Activity space, Legibility/Clarity. • Individual Freedom; Aesthetics, Control, Expression, Privacy, Low cost. • Diversity; Aesthetics, Variety, Choice, Interest, Sensitivity”
Yücel & Yıldızci (2010)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activity and Uses, Diversity, • Accessibility, • Legibility, Comfort, Image, Security, Maintenance, Sense of Ownership”
Karadeniz (2019)	“Suitability for People with Special Needs, Indoor Space, Equipment Elements, Security, Cleaning, Planting, Activity Inadequacy, Accessibility, Suitability for All Age Groups”
Öztürk & Temel (2019)	Spatial Attractiveness, Pedestrian Circulation, Disabled Access and Use, Indoor-Outdoor Spaces, Accessories, Flooring, Vegetative Elements, Water Elements, Artistic Objects”
Sarı (2019)	Physical, Functional, Aesthetic, Ecological
Yazici (2019)	Suitability, Safety, Cost, Durability, Serviceability, Performance, Aesthetics
Akten & Sunar (2022)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Function” Design should be useful for everyone. • Layout” Design should be easily understood. • Identity” The design should be distinctive and recognizable. • Attraction” Design should be pleasant and attractive.
Öner & Özbayraktar (2023)	• “Accessibility, Comfort, Central Role of Management”

In this context, 9 basic criteria and 81 sub-criteria and indicators were determined as urban park quality criteria (Table 4).

Table 4. Basic and sub-criteria for determining urban park quality performance

Basic criteria	Number of Sub-criteria	Number of Sub-criteria
Spatial Usability	7	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Usability of spaces for different purposes and according to all user characteristics • Social and cultural utilization • Mass to Void Ratio (%) • The degree of perceived openness/closedness of the space for users • Design Activities / Sufficiency of the number of activities • Ensuring interaction and integrity between the use of different spaces • Current carrying capacity of the park • Adequacy of seating and resting places
Plant Design and Suitability for Use	14	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consideration of design elements and principles (color, texture, line, scale) in plant compositions • Plant species use according to aesthetic and functional

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> purpose • Use of plant scales according to the scale of space • Use of the autumn color effect in plants • Use of grass, ground cover and herbaceous plants • Use case of color effect in plants • - Use of fragrant plant species • Use of flower cushions or flower beds • Use of plants against wind, dust, excessive sun and noise • The case for vegetative design to cover unwanted images • Integrity of plant design and structural materials when used together • Use of plants in terms of pruning and shaping • Adequacy of irrigation technique applied to crops • Utilization status of edible plant species
Ecosystem Services	7	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trees used in the park improve air quality, reduce soil erosion, reduce carbon dioxide emissions, and make significant contributions to the park ecosystem • The adequacy of the carbon sequestration capacity of the urban park can be improved • The amount of green space in the park is sufficient to serve the ecosystem • The status of including species other than ornamental plants in the urban park area (leafy natural species, fruit trees, natural ground covers alternative to grass, carbon forests) • Use of plants for energy conservation (cooling effects of plants in summer, reduction of wind in winter by screening, and better distribution of sunlight in winter by deciduous trees) • Protection of biodiversity through plant designs and planning • Hiding noise pollution and unwanted images with the plant species used
Structure/Material Design and Suitability for Use	12	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Buildings and facilities have local and original architectural typology • Aesthetic and functional use of structural furniture and fittings • Aesthetic and functional use of floor covering materials • Existence and adequacy of drainage system • Existence and adequacy of existing infrastructure systems (electricity, drinking water, sewage, etc.) • Reflection of identity values on fittings and furniture • Adequacy of lighting elements • Adequacy of garbage bins • Adequacy of seating elements • Adequacy of guidance and information staff • Adequacy of water facilities • Adequacy of food and water bowls for animals
Aesthetic (Visual and Auditory) Compliance	7	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Balanced, harmonious use of plant materials • Compatibility of plant and structural diversity with the environment • Proportion compatibility of elements in the space • Ensuring continuity in circulation within the park • Ensuring long-term activity and vitality due to its location and surrounding development • Adequacy of plant and structural diversity • Reducing noise impact in recreational areas through vegetative design integrity
Transportation	11	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The relationship of the entrances and exits of the park with the

and Accessibility		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> environment • Parking (Indoor and Outdoor) Capacity • Adequacy of in-park vehicle transportation • Adequacy of pedestrian transportation within the park • Adequacy of transportation such as bicycles, scooters, etc. in the park • Adequacy of public transportation to the park • Status of warning and directional signs for transportation • Use of stairs and ramps • Spatial accessibility for the physically disabled in the park • Use as an emergency assembly area • Appropriateness of the main axis and secondary axis relationship in the park
Comfort, Perception and Image Status	7	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reflection of local identity • User satisfaction • Provision of technological facilities (Internet, security cameras, charging for electronic devices, etc.) • Provision of basic needs such as eating/drinking, WC etc. • The effect of space forms on human perception • Usability of water as a visual and auditory aesthetic value • The suitability of the park for common use for individuals of all ages
Social Communication Level	8	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adequacy of social facilities • Adequacy of social activities and organizations • Frequency of users' use of the park • Contribution of users to the park and volunteering status • Feasibility level of active and passive recreational activities • Use of artistic elements • Availability of clean air • Environmental pollution status
Management and Governance	8	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Security situation (Controlled entrance and exit, 24 hour attendants, etc.) • Status of regular cleaning and maintenance • Adequacy of technical staff (Landscape Architect, etc.) • Employee auxiliary staff status • Inspection status within the park • Status of management's activities in the park • Level of participation of relevant stakeholders in management and governance • Status of improvement works in the park
Total	81	

The level of importance of the main and sub-criteria for determining urban park quality performance was determined by asking 50 different experts. The experts consisted of landscape architects (10 people), urban planners (10 people), architects (10 people), municipal administrators (10 people), park users who know the park (10 people). The weight scoring of the criteria was evaluated using Likert 3-point scoring technique (unimportant: 1 point, moderately important: 3 points, very important: 5 points).

According to the basic and sub-criteria obtained, a survey and evaluation form was created in the case of Söke Urban Zeytindalı Urban Park and the quality performance score of the park was determined according to the performance criteria / sub-criteria and indicators. The total score of each basic criterion according to its sub-criteria was multiplied by the weight score of the basic criterion. Thus, the sum of the scores of the main criterion was calculated as the total quality performance score of the park. The total performance evaluation indicators obtained were evaluated as "Very Low", 'Moderate' and "Very High".

In this context, the performance quality assessment indicators were multiplied by the weight score of each core criterion by taking into account the minimum (Min.SCn) and maximum (Max. SCn) scores of the total number of sub-criteria (SCn) of each core criterion. Thus, 3 different performance quality indicator ranges were determined by subtracting the difference between the minimum score (9.14) and maximum score (45.7) values (Table 5).

Table 5. Urban Parks performance quality assessment indicator ranges

Basic Criteria	Weight Score (Wsc)	Number of Sub-criteria (SCn)	If the Number of Sub-criteria scores Minimum 1 point, Total Score Min SCn	If the Number of Sub-criteria scores Minimum 1 point, Total Score Min SCn	If the Number of Sub-criteria scores Maximum 5 points, Total Score Max SCn Multiplying the Number of Sub-criteria by the Weight Score (WscxMin SCn)	If the Number of Sub-criteria scores Maximum 5 points, Multiplying the Number of Sub-criteria by the Weight Score (WscxMax.SCn)
Spatial Usability	0,13	7	7	35	0,91	4,55
Plant Design and Suitability for Use	0,13	14	14	70	1,82	9,1
Ecosystem Services	0,13	7	7	35	0,91	4,55
Structure/Material Design and Suitability for Use	0,12	12	12	60	1,44	7,2
Aesthetic (Visual and Auditory) Compliance	0,12	7	7	35	0,84	4,2
Transportation and Accessibility	0,12	11	11	55	1,32	6,6
Comfort, Perception and Image Status	0,1	7	7	35	0,7	3,5
Social Communication Level	0,08	8	8	40	0,64	3,2
Management and Governance	0,07	8	8	40	0,56	2,8
Total		81	81	405	9,14	45,7

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Determination of Urban Park Quality Criteria and Weight Scoring of Sub-Criteria

Various academic studies have been conducted on the quality assessment of urban parks and different basic criteria have been used. For example; Gülersoy et al. (2009) used criteria such as livability, survival character, connectivity, mobility, individual freedom, diversity. Yücel & Yıldızci (2010) considered criteria such as activities and uses, diversity, accessibility, legibility, comfort, image, safety, maintenance, sense of ownership. Karadeniz (2019) stated that criteria such as suitability for people with special needs, indoor space, equipment elements, security, cleaning, planting, lack of activity, accessibility, suitability for all age groups should be considered. Öztürk & Temel (2019) suggested criteria such as 'spatial attractiveness, pedestrian circulation, disabled access and use, indoor-outdoor spaces, equipment, flooring, vegetation, water elements, artistic objects.

The criteria used in these previous studies were evaluated and many sub-headings such as spatial composition, vegetative design, ecosystem services, orientation systems, material use and management processes were further elaborated. Nine main criteria and 81 sub-criteria were identified to be used in Zeytindalı Urban Park. It provides a comprehensive framework for assessing the quality performance of urban parks.

Compared to previous studies, most of the studies consider a limited number of criteria such as physical characteristics of the park, landscape quality and user satisfaction, while this study evaluates both physical and governance criteria together.

In order to determine the urban park quality performance, the importance levels of the basic and sub-criteria were determined by asking 50 different experts. The experts consisted of landscape architects (10 people), urban planners (10 people), architects (10 people), municipal administrators (10 people), park users who know the park (10 people). The weight scoring of the criteria was evaluated using Likert 3-point scoring technique (unimportant: 1 point, moderately important: 3 points, very important: 5 points). The general profile of the experts is given in Table 6.

Table 6. General profile of experts

Expert Features	Yüzde (%)	
Cinsiyet	Male	48
	Female	52
Age Groups	18-35	20
	36-70	75
	70+	5
Residence	City of Söke	83
	City of Aydın	9
	Districts of Aydın	5
	Other cities	3
Profession	Architect	20
	Landscape Architect	25
	Urban Planner	20
	Civil Engineer	8
	Teacher	2
	Tradesman	7
	Operator	3
	Environmental Engineer	2
	Forest Engineer	1
	Student	10
Other	2	
Institution Information	University	22
	Municipalities	38
	Official Institutions and Organizations	29
	Organizations	11
	City people	

Table 7. Scores and weight scores of key criteria according to experts

Criteria	the Weight Score
Spatial Usability	0,13
Plant Design and Suitability for Use	0,13
Ecosystem Services	0,13
Structure/Material Design and Suitability for Use	0,12
Aesthetic (Visual and Auditory) Compliance	0,12
Transportation and Accessibility	0,12
Comfort, Perception and Image Status	0,10
Social Communication Level	0,08
Management and Governance	0,07
Total	1,00

According to Table 7, spatial usability encompasses the assessments of different professional disciplines and user groups on the ability of the space to provide accessibility, user-friendliness and diversity. Landscape architects and urban planners focused on the integrity of the design, municipal managers emphasized management and maintenance priorities, and park users evaluated the social and cultural opportunities they directly experienced. These differences highlight the importance of interdisciplinary collaboration in space design and management. The total scores indicate the sustainability of the design as well as meeting user needs. In conclusion, a user-centered and interdisciplinary approach should be adopted to increase spatial usability.

Appropriateness of plant design and use plays a critical role in the sustainable planning of parks in terms of aesthetics and functionality. In this context, the ratings given by professional groups to these criteria make the contribution of their areas of expertise to the process evident. Landscape architects make significant contributions to the appropriate use of design elements such as color, texture and form of plants and to achieving aesthetic goals. Urban planners are influential on the integration of plants into the spatial layout and their harmony with the urban context, while architects focus on the harmony of plants with structural design and spatial integrity. Municipal administrators contribute to the development of sustainable management policies by supporting technical and implementation processes related to the use of plants. Park users' perceptions and satisfaction with these criteria are decisive in assessing whether the designs function effectively. This evaluation emphasizes the importance of inter-specialty integration and plant use in the context of aesthetics, functionality and sustainability.

When evaluated in the context of ecosystem services criteria, a significant interaction and difference is observed between professional disciplines. Landscape architects score high on protecting the ecological balance of the city and designing vegetation in a sustainable manner, while municipal administrators focus more on administrative aspects and strategies to protect the existing ecosystem. Urban planners assessed macro-level ecosystem services such as the carbon sequestration capacity of parks and the expansion of green spaces as part of general planning principles. Park users, on the other hand, focus on more directly observable factors such as the impact of the amount of green space on air quality based on individual experiences. These differences show that multidisciplinary approaches enrich decision-making processes related to ecosystem services, but interdisciplinary communication and collaboration are critical in this process.

An analysis of the criteria under the heading "Building/material design and suitability for use" reveals the multidimensional evaluation requirements of the field. Landscape architects and structural architects give high priority to both the visual and environmental compatibility of structures and

materials, generally considering aesthetics and functionality together. Urban planners focus more on sustainability and social functionality, while municipal administrators focus more on practical considerations such as budget, ease of management and maintenance costs. Park users, based on their own experiences, prioritize comfort, safety and accessibility over aesthetics. All these different perspectives emphasize the need for a multidisciplinary approach to building/material design and suitability for use. According to the research findings, the high scores given by landscape architects and architects indicate that these two professional groups play a key role in design and material selection. However, it was observed that the scores of municipality managers provide important contributions from a managerial and maintenance perspective and are decisive in the final decision-making processes. This clearly demonstrates that the design and suitability for use processes require interdisciplinary communication and collaboration.

In the category of aesthetic (audio-visual) appropriateness, there is a remarkable distribution between the contributions of the disciplines to these appropriateness criteria. Landscape architects and urban planners received significant points for aesthetic perception, focusing on the spatial organization and audiovisual compatibility of designs. It can be evaluated that landscape architects play an active role especially in terms of criteria such as the visual diversity of the parks, the compatibility of the spatial arrangement progression and the integration of vegetal diversity with visual aesthetics. Urban planners, on the other hand, emphasized the relationship of park entrances and exits with the environment and aesthetic dimensions in general spatial arrangements.

On the other hand, the contributions of architects in this category were characterized by emphasizing the aesthetic dimensions of the structural elements, while municipality administrators made evaluations from the perspective of general management and user satisfaction. The park users' high ratings in this category can be considered as user feedback on how impressive the visual and auditory perception they directly experienced was. This suggests that the aesthetic appropriateness of the park is considered in a balanced way for all user groups, but that landscape architects and users in particular attach higher importance to these criteria.

Transportation and accessibility play a critical role in the functional and user-friendly design of the park. The scoring shows that landscape architects, urban planners, architects, municipal administrators and park users similarly assess the importance of these criteria. Criteria such as parking capacity, spatial accessibility, and the effectiveness of transportation signage were rated highly due to interdisciplinary collaboration. This shows that each discipline has made a contribution appropriate to its area of expertise and that the park offers a design potential that is compatible with the environment and can respond to user needs.

When the evaluation of the professional disciplines under the heading "Comfort, perception and image status" is analyzed, it is seen that the park areas exhibit a general compatibility in terms of user satisfaction, emphasis on local identity, technological infrastructure facilities and the ability to meet basic needs. In this category, the contributions of field experts such as "Landscape Architects" and "Urban Planners" in bringing natural and structural elements together came to the fore. However, municipality management and park users also contributed highly to these criteria, providing a clearer perspective on the ground through their observations of user satisfaction. The data shows that the participating professional disciplines worked in a balanced way on elements such as the integration of technological facilities and accessibility of services, adopting an approach that enhances aesthetic perception and user satisfaction. This supports both the functionality and user-oriented design of park spaces and provides an important reference for the sustainability of spatial identity.

The criteria determined under the heading of social communication level provide a comprehensive evaluation of the potential of spatial design to facilitate the social interactions of individuals. When the "Scoring of indicators according to sub-criteria for the criterion of social communication level" is analyzed, a significant harmony is observed in the general evaluations of disciplines and users under this heading. While landscape architects and urban planners give high scores to elements such as the organization of social activities and the support of spatial elements for communication between

individuals, it is noteworthy that municipal administrators and park users also give weight to these aspects. This situation reveals that design should be user-oriented and the importance of a common understanding between disciplines. In particular, the scores given for criteria such as the use of art and recreation areas show that the multifaceted use and social sustainability of the park are supported. However, the commonalities in the evaluations emphasize that the level of social communication should be strengthened not only through physical arrangements, but also through participatory management and event planning.

The management and governance criteria include security, staff competence and maintenance-repair processes for the effective functioning of the parks, and landscape architects, architects and municipal administrators scored high on these criteria. Users, on the other hand, scored lower due to their limited participation in management processes. While this highlights the contribution of professional groups with management responsibilities to the functioning of the park, it shows that taking user feedback into account and increasing interdisciplinary cooperation is critical for the sustainability of the park.

3.2. Determination of Quality Performance within the Scope of Söke Zeytindalı City Park

Zeytindalı City Park is the most important and most used city park of Söke city. The city park was established in 2018 and has many functions and activity areas (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Zeytindalı Urban Park (From author's archive)

General characteristics obtained as a result of the survey conducted in the urban park;

-Spatial usability: There are park entrance signs. The entrance is recognizable for new users due to the location of the park. There are businesses, children's playgrounds, sports equipment, walking paths, seating areas in the park area.

-Pedestrian Circulation: Road circulation is compatible with each other and accessibility within the area is functional for all audiences.

-Disabled Access and Use: The park is designed so that disabled people can spend time comfortably and there are no special usage areas for the disabled.

-Indoor-Outdoor Spaces: There is a food and beverage area belonging to the municipality within the park. The establishment has both indoor and outdoor seating areas. There is also a WC and storage area.

-Accessories: As shown in Figure 6, there are different types of seating areas (20 benches, 36 picnic tables, etc.), garbage bins (23), lighting elements (57), direction and information signs in sufficient number and in good condition in terms of durability. Children's playgrounds (slides, zip lines, swings, seesaws), sports equipment (pull-up bars, waist stretching, bicycles and steppers, double walking, shoulder and arm training, body building equipment) are also in good and sufficient condition. While aesthetics come to the forefront in the design features of the lighting elements (such as material, dimensions, form, color), after dark, their functionality and features compatible with the environment come to the fore.

-Floor Coverings: Different types of flooring such as slate, rubber, grass, etc. were used in each area (Figure 6).

-Vegetative Elements: The area is rich in vegetation and designed with functionality in mind. Privacy is provided with hedge plants. Shade trees were preferred in the activity areas. For example, the abundance of olive trees in the area is the subject of the name of the park. In addition, the collection of olives and auctioning them also provides economic income. The plants used in the plant design are *Cortaderia selloana* (Schult.) Asch. & Graebn., *Rosmarinus officinalis* L., *Phormium tenax* variegata, *Pittosporum tobira* W.T.Aiton, *Matricaria chamomilla* L., *Lavandula angustifolia* Mill., *Santolina chamaecyparissus* L., *Muhlenbergia capillaris* L., *Laurus nobilis* L., *Cycas revoluta* Thunb., *Ligustrum japonicum* Thunb., *Lonicera periclymenum* L., *Platanus orientalis* L., *Agapanthus africanus* L. Hoffmanns., *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* Dehnh., *Cupressus sempervirens* L., *Viburnum lantana* L., *Berberis aquifolium* Pursh, *Cupressus × leylandii* A.B.Jacks. & Dallim. *Miscanthus sinensis* Andersson, *Juniperus communis* L., *Kniphofia uvaria* L. Oken, *Photinia serrulata* Lindl., *Strelitzia reginae* Banks, *Nerium oleander* L., *Osteospermum ecklonis* (DC) Norl., *Olea europaea* L., etc.

-Water Element: Water elements were used in the area in accordance with the design.

-Artistic Objects: The entrance tags are designed with cotton and olive objects, one of the important elements of the city, and sculptures.

Photographs showing the functions of the city park are given in Figures 6 and 7.

Figure 6. View of Zeytindalı City Park (From authors' archive)

Figure 7. Zeytindalı City Park night view (From authors' archive)

In order to determine the quality performance of Zeytindalı Urban Park in Söke, a performance score was obtained by using the KE-PA-KA-P model. For this purpose, a survey was conducted in the park and a total performance score was obtained according to the scores given in the evaluation forms. The evaluation forms and scores are given below.

The scoring of the indicators according to the sub-criteria for the “Spatial Usability Criterion” by the experts is shown in Table 8.

Table 8. Scoring of indicators according to sub-criteria for spatial usability criterion

Key Criterion	Weighting Scor	Sub-criteria	Scoring
Spatial Usability	0.13	• Usability of spaces for different purposes and for all user characteristics	5
		• Social and cultural use	3
		• (Mass to Space Ratio (%) The degree of openness/closedness of the space as perceived by users	3
		• Design Activities / Sufficiency of number of activities	1
		• Ensuring interaction and integrity between the use of different spaces	3
		• Current carrying capacity of the park	3
		• Adequacy of seating and resting areas	3
		Total Score	21
		Total Quality Performance Score (21x0,13)	2,73

The scoring of the indicators by the experts according to the sub-criteria for the “Appropriateness of Plant Design and Use Criterion” is shown in Table 9.

Table 9. Scoring of indicators according to sub-criteria for plant design and suitability for use criterion

Key Criterion	Weighting Scor	Sub-criteria	Scoring
Plant Design and Appropriateness of Use	0.13	• Consideration of design elements and principles (color, texture, form, line, scale) in plant compositions	3
		• Plant species use according to aesthetic and functional purpose	5
		• Use of plant scales according to spatial scale	5
		• Use of the autumn color effect in plants	3
		• Use of grass, ground cover and herbaceous plants	5
		• Use case of color effect in plants	5
		• Use of fragrant plant species	1
		• Use of flower beds or flower beds	3
		• Use of plants against wind, dust, excessive sun and noise	3
		• The case of vegetative design to cover unwanted images	3
		• Integrity of plant design and structural materials when used together	3
		• Use of plants in terms of pruning and shaping	3
		• Adequacy of irrigation technique applied to plants	5
		• Use of edible plant species	1
		Total Score	48
		Total Quality Performance Score (48x0,13)	6,24

The scoring of the indicators according to the sub-criteria for the “Ecosystem Services Criterion” by the experts is shown in Table 10.

Table 10. Scoring of indicators according to sub-criteria for ecosystem services (sustainability between human and nature) criterion

Key Criterion	Weighting Scor	Sub-criteria	Scoring
Ecosystem Services	0.12	• Trees used in the park make significant contributions to the park ecosystem by improving air quality, reducing soil erosion, reducing carbon dioxide emissions, etc.	5
		• The adequacy of the carbon sequestration capacity of the city park can be improved	5
		• The amount of green space in the park is sufficient to serve the ecosystem	5
		• The extent to which species other than ornamental plants are included in the urban park area (leafy natural species, fruit trees, natural ground covers alternative to grass, carbon forests)	3
		• Use of plants to save energy (cooling effects of plants in summer, reducing wind in winter by screening, and better distribution of sunlight in winter by deciduous trees)	5
		• Protection of biodiversity through plant designs and planning	5
		• Concealment of noise pollution and unwanted images with the plant species used	3
		Total Score	31
		Total Quality Performance Score(31x0,12)	4,03

The scoring of the indicators by the experts according to the sub-criteria for the “Appropriateness of Construction/Material Design and Use Criterion” is shown in Table 11.

Table 11. Scoring of indicators according to sub-criteria for the criterion of building/material design and suitability for use

Key Criterion	Weighting Scor	Sub-criteria	Scoring
Building/Material Design and Suitability for Use	0.12	• Buildings and facilities have a local and original architectural typology	3
		• Aesthetic and functional use of structural furniture and fittings	5
		• Aesthetic and functional use of floor covering materials	5
		• Existence and adequacy of drainage system	3
		• Existence and adequacy of existing infrastructure systems (electricity, drinking water, sewage, etc.)	5
		• Reflection of identity values on fittings and furniture	5
		• Adequacy of lighting elements	1
		• Adequacy of garbage bins	3
		• Adequacy of seating elements	3
		• Adequacy of guidance and information boards	3
		• Adequacy of water reinforcement	3
		• Adequacy of food and water bowls for animals	3
		Total Score	42
		Total Quality Performance Score(42x0,12)	5,04

The scoring by the experts according to the sub-criteria for the “Aesthetic (Visual and Auditory) Appearance Criterion” is shown in Table 12.

Table 12. Scoring of indicators according to sub-criteria for aesthetic (visual and auditory) appearance criterion

Key Criterion	Weighting Scor	Sub-criteria	Scoring
Aesthetic (Visual and Auditory) Appropriateness	0.12	• Balanced and harmonious use of plant materials	3
		• Compatibility of plant and structural diversity with the environment	3
		• Proportion compatibility of elements in the space	5
		• Continuity in circulation within the park	5
		• Ensuring long-term activity and vitality due to its location and surrounding development	5
		• Adequacy of plant and structural diversit	3
		• Reducing noise impact in recreational areas through vegetative design integrity	3
		Total Score	27
		Total Quality Performance Score (27x0,12)	3,24

Transportation and Accessibility Status Criterion" by the experts according to the sub-criteria is shown in Table 13.

Table 13. Scoring of indicators according to sub-criteria for the transportation and accessibility status criterion

Key Criterion	Weighting Scor	Sub-criteria	Scoring
Transportation and Accessibility	0.12	• The relationship of the entrances and exits of the park with the environment	3
		• Parking (Indoor and Outdoor) Capacity	1
		• Adequacy of in-park vehicle transportation	1
		• Adequacy of pedestrian transportation within the park	5
		• Adequacy of bicycle, scooter, etc. transportation in the park	5
		• Adequacy of public transportation to the par	5
		• Status of warning and directional signs for transportation	1
		• Use of stairs and ramps	3
		• Spatial accessibility for the physically disabled in the park	1
		• Use as an emergency assembly area	3
		• Relevance of the main axis and secondary axis relationship in the park	3
		Total Score	31
		Total Quality Performance Score (31x0,12)	3,72

The scoring by the experts according to the sub-criteria for the “Comfort, Perception and Image Status Criterion” is shown in Table 14.

Table 14. Scoring of indicators according to sub-criteria for the comfort, perception and image status criterion

Key Criterion	Weighting Score	Sub-criteria	Scoring
Comfort, Perception and Image	0.10	• Reflection of local identity	3
		• User satisfaction level	5
		• Provision of technological facilities (Internet, security camera, charging for electronic devices, etc.)	1
		• Provision of basic needs such as eating/drinking, WC etc	5
		• The effect of space forms on human perception	5
		• Usability of water as a visual and auditory aesthetic value	5
		• Suitability of the park for common use by individuals of all ages	5
		Total Score	29
		Total Quality Performance Score (29x0,10)	2,9

The scoring by the experts according to the sub-criteria for the “Social Communication Level Criterion” is shown in Table 15.

Table 15. Scoring of indicators according to sub-criteria for the social communication level criterion

Key Criterion	Weighting Score	Sub-criteria	Scoring
Level of Social Communication	0.08	• Adequacy of social facilities	3
		• Adequacy of social activities and organizations	3
		• Frequency of users using the park	5
		• Contribution of users to the park and volunteering status	1
		• Feasibility level of active and passive recreational activities	5
		• Use of artistic elements	1
		• Availability of clean air	5
		• Environmental pollution status	5
		Total Score	28
Total Quality Performance Score (28x0,08)	2,24		

The scoring by the experts according to the sub-criteria for the “Management and Governance Criterion” is shown in Table 16.

Table 16. Scoring of indicators according to sub-criteria for the management and governance criterion

Key Criterion	Weighting Score	Sub-criteria	Scoring
Management and Governance	0.07	• Security situation (Controlled entrance and exit, 24-hour attendance, etc.)	1
		• Regular cleaning and maintenance	5
		• Qualification of technical staff (Landscape Architect, etc.)	5
		• Availability of auxiliary staff	5
		• Inspection status within the park	5
		• Status of management's activities in the park	3
		• Level of participation of relevant stakeholders in management and governance	3
		• Status of improvement activities in the park	3
		Total Score	30
Total Quality Performance Score (30x0,07)	2,1		

As a result, a total performance score of 32.24 was obtained as a result of the evaluations made using the KE-PA-KA-P model in the Zeytindalı Urban Park of Söke City. Accordingly, it is determined that the quality performance value of the Park has a “**Medium Level**” performance.

The quality performance evaluation score of Zeytindalı Urban Park is shown in Table 17.

Table 17. Total quality performance evaluation score of Zeytindalı Urban Park

Criteria	Weight Score	Total Score of Sub-criteria	Mean Scores
Spatial Usability	0,13	21	2,73
Plant Design and Suitability for Use	0,13	48	6,24
Ecosystem Services	0,13	31	4,03
Structure/Material Design and Suitability for Use	0,12	42	5,04
Aesthetic (Visual and Auditory) Appropriateness	0,12	27	3,24
Transportation and Accessibility	0,12	31	3,72
Comfort, Perception and Image	0,1	29	2,9
Social Communication Level	0,08	28	2,24
Management and Governance	0,07	30	2,1
TTotal (total 50 people)		287	32,24

4. Conclusion and Suggestions

Public green areas in and around cities are the most important components of urban life. They play a very important role in terms of urban life quality. In order to obtain the desired services and contributions in urban areas, especially city parks, national gardens and recreational areas, it requires a holistic approach to planning/design and sustainable management. In this context, monitoring, observing and determining the quality performance of city parks and national gardens built with great effort and devotion at high costs is of great importance for sustainable and effective management. Thus, it will also enable studies to be carried out for improvement and development.

For this purpose, basic/sub-criteria for determining the quality criteria and performance of urban parks were determined. An urban parks quality performance (KE-PA-KA-P) model that can be used for urban parks and public green spaces in our country has been created.

In the application of this model, 9 main quality criteria (*Spatial Usability, Plant Design and Suitability for Use, Ecosystem Services, Building/Material Design and Suitability for Use, Aesthetic (Visual and Auditory) Suitability, Transportation and Accessibility, Comfort, Perception and Image, Level of Social Communication and Management and Governance*) were considered. In addition, a total of 81 sub-criteria related to the main criteria were used. Thus, this study has a unique characteristic in terms of using more basic/sub-criteria than the criteria used in the literature and determining the quality performance of existing urban parks with this model.

Since Söke Zeytindalı City Park is located in the center of Söke, it is one of the areas with high usage potential and appeals to a wide range of user profiles. This park serves as a meeting and sharing place in terms of activity, functionality and interaction. Therefore, the model approach was tested in Söke Zeytindalı City Park. As a result of the scores given to the main/sub-criteria used in this model, the total quality performance score of Söke Zeytindalı City Park was 32.24. Accordingly, the quality performance value of the Park is determined as “medium level”.

According to this result, it has been revealed that Zeytindalı City Park needs some improvement and development in order to increase user satisfaction and quality, especially according to the main/sub-criteria with low scores.

In this context; Improving the physical and social infrastructure of Zeytindalı City Park, making spatial arrangements more functional, increasing user diversity, enriching plant species and composition with local species, arranging seasonal color transitions and arranging them in a way to increase visual

appeal, using water elements and artistic elements in terms of aesthetics, prioritizing sustainability in building and material choices, choosing environmentally friendly and durable materials, In order to increase the accessibility of the park, suggestions such as improving public transportation options, developing alternative transportation options such as bicycle and pedestrian paths, making arrangements for disabled individuals in accordance with universal design principles, restructuring the management and governance processes of the park based on user feedback, taking the opinions of the public through regular surveys and workshops, creating a transparent and participatory management model, informing them about activities and services through digital platforms, etc. were made. The implementation of these recommendations will enable Zeytindalı City Park to become a social and ecological center of attraction at the urban scale.

The most important advantage of this model approach is that it is easy and applicable for every urban park. It also reveals the holistic current state of the area, saves time, can be evaluated with at least two people, and the number of sub-criteria can be changed or increased. The weight scoring of the main criteria can be optimized even if they differ according to the experts. Ultimately, this model will serve as a guide for managers by identifying all the deficiencies of the park.

Improving the aesthetic and functional quality of urban parks will lead to an increase in the quality of urban life. Evaluating the performance of urban parks during their use is important in terms of identifying and solving the problems of these parks. For this reason, the quality performance of urban parks should be monitored periodically, deficiencies should be identified and strategic actions should be envisaged.

As a final word; the quality of life of cities is directly related to the purposeful, sustainable and high quality services and contributions of public green spaces.

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